

NIGERIAN THEATRE JOURNAL

ISSN 0189-9562

Editor
Dr. Jenks Zakari Okwori

Editorial Board Members
Dr. L. Bamidele
Dr. Saint Gbileka

Editorial Consultants
Mr. Duro Oni
Dr. Jide Malorno
Professor Akanji Nasiru
Dr Olu Akomolafe
Professor Olu Obafetni
Dr. Hyginus Ekwuu/i
Professor Iyonvuese Haglter
Professor Dapo Adelugba

Copyright

Society of Nigerian Theatre Artists, 2002

Designed & Produced
by

Dat & Partners Logistics Ltd.

135, Oshodi Rd., Orllc Oshodi, Oshodi, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Tel: 08037180343. 234 - 802 - 2234554, E-mail: daundpartnersOdV aho0.com

EDITOR'S NOTE

The Nigerian State is into its fourth Republic in democratic experiment, it has not become only expedient to examine how the leadership has performed but also how democracy has performed and indeed how the citizens have performed. Nowhere is this interview as cogent as in the realm of theatre and performing arts, precisely because theatre do not only mirror, reflect and mediate life but significantly also instigate it. This journal is the product of a journey undertaken during the last SONTA Convention and Annual Conference into "Performing Identities: Theatre and the State in Nigeria."

A crucial aspect of the Nigerian experience is the question of citizenship and identity. What identities are we projecting and why? Do we feel the sense of being Nigerians⁹ How have theatre and performing arts been implicated in defining, articulating and projecting these identities?

The articles here implicate theatre and performing arts as multidisciplinary enterprises that derive their relevance from their ability to be tools, methodologies or strategies for research enlightenment, entertainment or better-put edutainment and consciousness raising.

The papers here try to generate debates and discussions around the issues that shape the nature and manner of present day Nigeria and prospect for progressive ways forward. In Kaduna State identities are played out daily via the artistic forms of expression of the people. Here the people have developed coping and resistance mechanisms for dealing with their oppression and deprivation in the Nigerian State by performing their lives.

This way they not only ensure that their problems are always kept under constant discourse but that the people are constantly mobilized to keep searching for ways out. In other instances, some of the papers are questioning the cultural and economic import of the homevideo explosion in Nigeria. Instead of projecting a Nigerian identity, the papers argue people are performing their differences. This is an adequate testament to the fears expressed by many that the Nigerian experiment still remains an experiment.

Yet some of the papers draw upon residual cultural forms to perform uniqueness. The Yoruba and Ibibio are examples of peoples who define their existence by patterns of life cultivated over a period of time before the birth of Nigeria.

Some of the articles show that performances of plays within the universities project and reify difference or differing identities by using costumes and make-up that emphasize such difference.

Even the representation of women for economic and cultural reasons thereby reinforcing identity stereotypes nurtured by a patriarchal society is not left out in this volume of the SONTA JOURNAL.

The crucial questions, which these papers pose, which continue to ricochet beyond the pages of this journal, include: is there a Nigerian identity? If in reality the constituent units of Nigeria are preoccupied with performing difference, can there really be a national culture or a Nigerian consciousness to which all Nigerians subscribe? Do Nigerians surrender their rights to the Nigerian State or to ethnic nationality consciousness? I doubt if any of the papers in this volume venture an answer to these questions beyond their explication and elaboration.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Nigerian Theatre Journal Vol 7. No. 1, 2002.

VI

- 1 Playing Identities: Dramatising Citizenship, Participation and Accountability in Kaduna State - Jenks Zakari Okwori, Department of English and Drama, Ahmadu Bello University.
- 2 Global Information Technology, Identity Consciousness and the Nigeria Home video Theatre Practice.- Emmy Idegu, Department of English and Drama, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- 3 The Nigerian Home Video Actor and National Identity - Edward S. Ossai, National Film Institute, Jos, Nigeria.
- 4 Installation/Sculpture as a Form of Identity: An Aesthetic Element of Performance Context in Nigeria -Tonie Okpe, Department of Fine Arts, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- 5 Of'Basics and Fragments': Foreign Cultural Agencies in Nigeria and the Nation's Performance Identity, - Bakare Ojo Rasaki, Department of Theatre Arts, University Of Uyo, IJyo.
- 6 The Secularization of Bata Dance in Nigeria, - Ojuade, Jeleel Olasunkanmi, Performing Arts Department, University Of Ilorin
- 7 Gender Politics and Drama: Re-Reading Soyinka's *He and the Jewel* -Muhammed O. Bhadmus, Department Of English, Bayero University Kano .
- 8 Interpreting Nigeria through Costume and Make-Up: An analysis of Ola Rotimi's *Grip 'Am* And Tracie Chima Utoh's *Forest Palmtrees*- Tracie Chima Utoh, Department of Theatre Arts, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka .

PROFESSOR
SHAMSUDEEN
O. O. AMALI

PROFESSOR
SHAMSUDEEN
O. O. AMALI

DEDICATION

On our way to the press for this publication the news came that Professor Shamsudeen O. O. Amali, a first rate and complete product of theatre has been made the Vice Chancellor of the University of Ilorin. By this feat Profesor Amali has become the First Theatre Arts Professor to be appointed a Vice Chancellor in Nigeria THIS PUBLICATION IS DEDICATED TO YOU PROFESSOR SHAMSUDEEN O. O. AMALI, VICE CHANCELLOR, UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN

PROFESSOR
SHAMSUDEEN
O. O. AMALI

PROFESSOR
SHAMSUDEEN
O. O. AMALI

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The editor and the National Executive Committee of the Society of Nigerian Theatre Artists wish to express our profound gratitude and thanks to the Vice Chancellor of Ahmadu Bello University, Professor Abdullahi Mahadi, for sponsoring the publication of this journal. We are also thankful to the Head, Department of English and Drama Dr., Sanni Abba Aliyu for his untiring support. What would be have done without the permission touse the facilities of the Theatre Alliance based in ABU? We and staff available to be used to typeset this journal for other logistical arrangements.

- 9 Preservation and Promotion of Indigenous cultural values through the Nigerian Television Prospects and problems - **Ubong Nda**, Department of Theatre Arts, University of Uyo
- 10 Durbar in Northern Nigeria: Towards the apprehension of the cultural imperative of power, - **M. I. Umar-Buratai**, Department of English and Drama, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- 11 The ABU Campus as Mini Nigeria in terms of dressing, how it influence the style of costumes in some Performances in ABU Studio Theatre, - **V.B. Lagwainpa**, Department of English and Drama, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
- 12 Three Female Playwrights In Nigeria: The Question of Identity - **Ngozi Udengwu**, Department of Dramatic Arts, University Of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- 13 Identity of the Ibibio Woman in Performance: A study of Mboppo and Ebre Dances, **Ifure Inieke Ufford**, department of Theatre Arts, University of Uyo, Uyo
- 14 Revenue Laundering by Image Blundering: A Recap of the Imagining of Women in some Nigerian Home Videos, - **Kayode Animasaun**, General Studies Department, The Federal Polytechnic, Bida.

**GLOBAL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, IDENTITY
CONSCIOUSNESS AND THE NIGERIAN HOME VIDEO
THEATRE PRACTICE**

EMMY UNUJA IDEGU

INTRODUCTION

The development of humanity in any given society is a resultant effect of variables. Of all facts or contributory factors to human and societal development, the role of information and information management has remained absolutely crucial. Of old, a number of wars were fought which could have (been averted if information flow was properly handled. Though instances of crises resulting from misinformation or poor handling of information outlets exist even in this generation, the advancement of information technology has immensely helped in reducing such avoidable crises. In pre-historic society indigenous forms of information dissemination were not only guarded seriously by the monarchs and powers that be, but personalities in charge of sue! aspects of societal responsibilities were no mean men. They were active, sensitive, articulate and versatile people.

The society is dynamic and so is the dynamism of information it is advancing with a speed hardly imaginable before now in its avowed vision of unifying several parts, not of a society, but of the world into a global village. The role of information technology in this global village, or globalisation in it entirely, has remained focal and vital in the whole process of inter-relatedness of humanity. Mike Kwanaishie (1998:342) observes that

The emergence and rapid expansion of the information super highway has brought to the door of people all over the world information which has become a vital factor in daily decision making. Remote areas around the world are today covered by the communication range through technological advances in cyberspace, in the computer and telecommunications field.

A positive and laudable as this impact of information dissemination may be, I lie opening which the information technology has created has impact on almost all aspects of human life (culture, religion and values are all affected as people all over the world are exposed, more than ever before, to different and alternative views). The fear of cultural imperialism therefore, underscores a point that globalisation would also be seen as process of harmonization of different cultures and beliefs (Mike Kwanaishie 1998: 341)

The globalisation of culture in this regard is not the same as its homogenisation but globalisation involves the use of a variety of instruments of homogenization (ornaments, advertising techniques, language and clothing styles) Much are absorbed into local political and cultural economies, only to be repatriated as heterogeneous dialogues of national sovereignty and free enterprise in which there is too much openness to global flows. Thus, the central feature of global culture is the politics of incorporation of the weak by the dominant’.

This accounts for the understandable apprehension in traditional societies Where there is some noticeable ‘mounting anxiety about the impact of mass and global entertainment on the daily life, men - women relationships, sexual morality and the obligations of parents and children. Old certainties about how human beings should behave have been shattered by new social and sexual mores that the global media have helped and are still helping to spread’. Increasingly, parents,- teachers and religious bodies are finding it very difficult1 not near impossible, to hold back these changes. Families find it tough to censor what their children and wards see or hear as they remain glued for loins on end to the cable networks on the television or dream away precious HI" with their contact with the global media than exercise their brains to cope with due education offered them in schools and at home. This is dangerous because ‘in an increasingly atomized society packaged fantasies serve **to cut** off real human relationships for which they substitute stereotypes’.

As traditional family authorities, especially the elite class, continue to weaken and public education tries to prepare Nigerian children to cope with the (responsibilities of citizenship or with the challenges of a changing market n| changing world, or to develop the critical facilities citizens need so as not 1 be gulled by their leaders, most children, the leaders of tomorrow, are being instructed by shadows on the global screens on how to become “precocious consumers”. They are under the influence of highly creative communicators with little or no interest at all in their education. What a global trap!.

IDENTITY CONSCIOUSNESS

The issue of how to respond to this global trap is a matter that has been attracting attention from people. This response comes in several ways, most of which attempt some level of self assertion and the redefinition, or reactivation of identity consciousness and the zeal not to loose one’s essence in this global village via information technology. People’s culture is a sensitive p of their being. When this aspect of their self esteem is being threatened negative influence, there is bound to be attendant moves to protect, preset and promote that which is theirs.

Culture is the element we inhabit as subject for culture embraces the whole range of practices, customs and representations in a society. In their rituals, stories and images, societies identify what they perceive as good and evil, proper and sexually acceptable. Culture is the initiation of values and the study of cultures shows how values vary from one society to another, or from one historical movement to the next. (Simon Malpas 2001: vii).

Identity consciousness is focused on a people’s culture because ‘if culture pervasive and constitutive for us, if it resides in the documents, objects a practices that surround us, if it circulates as the meanings and values we lez and reproduce as good citizens’, (Simon Malpas 2001 :vii), then its cont* with other cultures through whatever medium needs to be carefully protect because ‘a minor modification changes its essence and may alter the meani

of values, after all the introduction of a negative constructs a resistance'. Faced with information technology, what attempts are communities in Nigeria making to preserve and redefine their humanity, their essence and their identities in the confrontation against global information forces.

The issue of identity consciousness is crucial here because in as much as the World has become a global village, the world has nevertheless, remained "increasingly integrated" no doubt, but also "highly differentiated". Societies and peoples of the world often retreat to re-examine their identities in the face of this global threat. As they get bombarded by high information technology and its side affects on their indigenous value systems, they deliberately recoil into identity formation, identity re-organization or identity consciousness. This identity re-awakening is all 'about questions of using the resource of history, language and culture in the process of becoming rather Hum being; not 'who we are' or 'where we came from', so much as what we might become, how we have been presented and how that bears on how we might represent ourselves'. Stuart Hall (1996:4).

The emphasis here is that the alternative to high information technology via globalisation is found and articulated in the spheres of identity consciousness,, its relocation and reappraisal, placing it within the larger context of global forces, because identify itself is a structured representation which only achieves its positive through the narrow eyes of the negative. When a people's culture is threatened by the dominant hegemonic culture, there is that realisation to protect one's own identity and interest that is threatened. (Abiola Irele 1990:89). The return to this identity or its reawakening is what Frantz Fanon (1963:170) once termed a 'passionate research directed by the secret hope of discovering beyond the misery of today, beyond the self contempt, resignation and abjuration, some very beautiful and splendid era whose existence rehabilitates us both in regard to ourselves and in regards to others'. Our concern with identity in this paper is not grounded in archeology but in the retelling, re-interpreting, re-constructing and re-historicising of the past, our i' lions past which is threatened by the inglorious dominant global present.

The place of identity formation in this paper is both as a form of resistance against unfriendly cultural practices beamed globally through the advanced information technology and as an alternative information network to the global super highway.

THE NIGERIAN HOME VIDEO THEATRE INDUSTRY

The entire world today is experiencing an explosion of satellite communication network. This development is no doubt, dealing some deadly blows to our indigenous entertainment industries. Interestingly, this invasion of global (mostly western) is reawakening the appreciation of local cultural traditions. The influx of global cultures through foreign films and cable network to Nigeria, for example, encouraged the commencement of an alternative form of 'entertainment via the home video industry in Nigeria today. The return to the indigenous (home video) can be seen to be a response to globalisation, covertly or overtly.

Faced with a particular form of modernity (cable network, foreign programmes or films), Nigerian artistes are carving out what can be termed a 'globalising reaction to global compression and the intensity of global flows' It is at the 'retreated to' indigenous options that there are struggles for cultural representation. It is respect for indigenous roots which is drawn in and used against the anonymous impersonal forces of globalisation. (Henderson J. 976:68).

At a point that the film entertainment industry and cable television network had globalised themes of violence, sex, western life style, love and the like,' the Nigerian home video industry has come up to challenge, as it were, this 'universal' culture by promoting what the script writers, directors and producers see as countering the foreign or global influence with issues and indigenous themes and plot structures in their production that reflect our own identity or sometimes, their own understanding and interpretation of what our identity should be or rather, what they think our identity ought to be.

The long period of entertainment colonisation by the foreign media via their own type of films and currently the cable network has so affected us that the seeming indignation and hatred for the imported identities accounts for the over inspirational, and one dares say, over romanticized themes in some of the Nigerian home video productions who in their forceful urge towards identity consciousness, over flog some issues so treated, principal amongst which is fetishism and “African Juju This limitation and others notwithstanding, today, more Nigerian homes take pride in identifying with Nigerian home videos than foreign films. If for nothing, even with their obvious creative and artistic indigestion the Nigerian home video is **“our own”**”.

There is no gain saying the obvious that in the past Nigerians depended so much on foreign forms of entertainment. Many Nigerians, however, "lamented this development because they felt that the superimposition of Western values and culture on Nigeria could be detrimental to the moral and intellectual development of Nigerian youths and perhaps lead to the erosion of our cultural values . (Aleydeino, S. C 1994:560) . The case today had changed as many Nigerians now have access to Nigerian home video productions. This rise of video culture signifies the ‘emergence of a new kind of public sphere in Nigeria, one that is based on the privatization of media production and consumption’. (Jonathan Haynes 1997:106). This was never the case in both colonial times and the first decades of independence when

the state played a huge role in the sponsorship and regulation of media production and reception. But the contemporary video culture operates largely outside state control. The world Bank’s insistence on privatization as a precaution for financial aid has combined with the savage economic effects of this structural adjustment programme to decimate the funding , authority and morale of other state - based mass media. For the first time in Nigerian history, the social importance of electronic mass media, the public they create, the cultural worlds they invoke and make meaningful to Nigerian audiences, the space of political and religious communities they foster, are

being formed without significant state input. These are the wider sociological changes that have shaped video production in Nigeria and which give context to the reception of any particular video drama. (Jonathan Haynes 1997: 106).

There is need for caution in exercising this medium for promotion, propagation and even preservation of Nigerian culture. Obviously, the "ground had been prepared for Nigeria home video by the loud orchestrated campaign against the influx of western films which propagate western culture wholesale, with dreadful consequences for impressionable minds of the Nigerian youth who form the bulk of home video audiences. In this regard, the Nigerian home video producers, like the writers in the pre-and post independence eras, were expected not only to be social activists and nationalists, but also to be curators and good curators of our cultures'. (Jonathan Haynes 1997:100) It is the level to which this singular responsibility of the artiste is been successfully implored or otherwise that makes or mars the Nigeria home video theatre experiment.

Each section of the country, with its indigenous script writers, directors and producers seem to delve into some ethnic enclaves in this whole issue of identity formation. They project what their immediate society or people or target audience is known for The themes of the typical Hausa home video for instance, revolves around culture and morality, which are presented often in a classroom manner. Language and religion are major elements of culture. Islam is the dominant religion amongst the Hausas. It is also the dominant religion amongst other major northern ethnic groups like the Fulani, Kanuri and Nupe. The culture which the Hausa home video presents is the culture of the Hausa coated with Islam. Almost every other Hausa video anchors its thematic thrust and its story in the Hausa culture. This is not a bad idea at all. The typical Hausa producer could after all, not watch for long, other sections of the country promote their own identity. The same goes for the other producers from other parts of the country with each protecting and promoting "his own" identity

For the Hausa home video produces, their themes range from forced marriage, as in "Haukan Mutum" by Aminu Argungu, to conflicts of class versus individual desires, as in Ibrahim Mandwari's "Gimbiya Fatima". Most of them nevertheless, go around the themes of culture conflict and morality. These themes are never a prerogative of the Hausa home videos. They are universal. "Not without my Daughter", "Yasmiri" and "Mississippi Masala" are good examples from abroad. However, the elements of culture that are brought in are important only in so far as they contribute to our understanding of the plot and our total enjoyment of the video. (Jonathan Haynes 1997: 103).

With the Igbo (English sub-titled sometimes) films, the issue is cultural confusion. Their themes revolve around love, the quest for wealth, pleasure and power, but often the viewer is left confused as to the cultural point of view from which he is expected to look at the issues even as "the educated Igbo man is anguished".

For the typical Yoruba home video, the role and place of gods and their relationship with the living and the influence on human activities seem to dominate the thematic pre-occupation and plot structure of their home videos.

The response of various zones of the country to the home video phobia notwithstanding, records available show that the West, particularly the Lagos-Ibadan axis had made more impacts in this entertainment industry. Since the beginning of the 90's Lagos - Ibadan has churned out home videos at the rate of one per week, or even more. Within this same period the Kano - Kaduna axis has produced a total of not more than fifty-what Lagos would produce within a year. Abdukarim Mohammed of *Moving Image*, Kano, compiled a list of 40 home videos produced in Kano within this period, 35 of which are recordings by Drama clubs of their stage performances on VHS. To Abddkarim Mohammed only 5 of the 40 videos listed were produced by professionals. Professional video production is therefore an area that is still largely unexploited. (Jonathan Haynes 1997:100).

The point must nonetheless be made that the emotional influx into identity projection via home video productions without the artistry and professional experience does not mean well for the home video entertainment industry in Nigeria at all. The dash into home video production in Nigeria has confronted us with more dangerous consequences than cultural pollution. Could this poor outing of some Nigeria home video productions as creative works, of art, be the result of an ‘over emphasis on the call to use the medium as a tool for the promotion and propagation of culture, or the result simply of the inability of the directors, who are fascinated with the medium but do not have the discipline to grapple first with its forms and technicalities? Every home video is based in a particular culture which it silently or violently projects; but it must be remembered that it does this or should do this through mastery of the art and technique of the medium. (Jonathan Haynes 1997:100) Anything short of this, is a mockery of identity consciousness.

If the experiment in Nigerian home video theatre was intended to take up the challenge poised by the dominance of foreign cultures via foreign information dissemination media, then most Nigerian home videos have responded rather poorly. Most of them, especially the Yoruba and Igbo home videos by their reliance on “Juju” or fetishism, often seem to suggest, and very loudly too, that their culture is static or even backward looking. Art ‘without a cultural base is meaningless. But it must be art in the first place, aesthetically fulfilling. It is only then that art can effectively promote and propagate culture, and thereafter, consequently live to the tenets of identity consciousness, for after all, identity formation is not a transcendental spirit inside us on which history had made no fundamental marks. It is not a mere phantasm. It has its histories, and histories have their real material and symbolic effects. (Patrick Williams 1994:395). The onus lies on the Nigeria home video producers to reflect not just the history but the “symbolic effects” of that history of contemporary relevance to our today.

The producers should see the need to go back to our roots and expose our past with proper and adequate understanding of the effective communicative power of home videos as instruments of propagating ideas ideologies and certain standpoints in our endless quest for identity formation rather than negate it.

However, for the Nigerian home video theatre practice to satisfy the main thrust of its essence, the government, the producers and all stakeholders must as a matter of urgency and necessity, re-visit the drawing board, consider the ethical, technical, artistic and professional demands or implications of the industry over and above the immediate economic gains that jeopardize outrightly, the same interest they profess to protect Anything short of this redirection of the Nigerian home video industry amounts to an absolute negation of identity consciousness inherent in home video theatre as in dynamic and potent communicative medium.

Notes

Abiola Irele (1990), The African Experience in Literature and Ideology. Indiana University Press.

Aleydeino, S. C. (1994) "Education and occupational diversification among young learners: The problem of harmonizing traditional practices with lessons of our colonial heritage" in *Journal of issues in Development 1(1)*

"Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review, Vol. 36, 1998".

Frantz Fanon (1963), The Wretched of the Earth. Penguin, London.

Henderson J. (ed), (1976), Resistance Through Rituals, Hutchinson, London

Jonathan Haynes (ed), (1997), Nigeria Video Films. Kraft Books Ltd, Ibadan.

Simon Maipas (ed), (2001), Readers in Cultural Criticism :Postmodern Debates. Palgrave. New York.

Stuart Hall (ed), (1996) Questions of Cultural Identity, SAGE Publications, London.